

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17896550

Objective Structured Clinical Examination and its Application in Nursing and Midwifery Professional Examinations

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ABSTRACT

The Objective Structured Clinical Examination (OSCE) has emerged as a reliable and standardized method of assessing clinical competence in health professions education. Introduced by Harden in 1975, OSCE was designed to address the limitations of traditional clinical examinations, particularly examiner bias, lack of objectivity, and inconsistency. Unlike conventional assessments that focus mainly on theoretical knowledge, OSCE evaluates multiple domains of competence, including cognitive, psychomotor, and affective skills. This paper explores the application of OSCE in nursing and midwifery professional examinations in Nigeria. It highlights its structure, blueprinting process, station design, and implementation by the Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria (NMCN). Evidence from literature demonstrates that OSCE enhances fairness, improves student confidence, and ensures comprehensive evaluation of clinical skills. The paper concludes that effective integration of OSCE into nursing and midwifery examinations will produce competent, versatile professionals capable of delivering high-quality care.

Keywords: Clinical Examination, conventional assessments, nursing and midwifery examinations

INTRODUCTION

The Objective Structured Clinical Examination (OSCE) was first introduced by Harden in 1975 to overcome the shortcomings of traditional clinical assessments, which often lacked fairness, objectivity, and standardization. Traditional methods primarily assessed the cognitive domain, focusing on the “knows” and “knows how” levels of Miller’s pyramid of competence. In contrast, OSCE evaluates a wider range of domains, including cognitive, psychomotor, and affective skills, with particular emphasis on the “shows how” level of competence (Gupta et al., 2010; Harden, 1979; Miller, 1990).

OSCE emphasizes the demonstration of clinical skills rather than theoretical knowledge alone. Students are expected to master correct clinical methods, practice them repeatedly, and integrate theory with practice (Pallipedia, 2021). Adequate preparation, including formative or mock OSCEs, has been shown to build confidence and competence (Street & Hamilton, 2010; Alinier, 2003).

By breaking down competencies into smaller, observable tasks such as history taking, physical examination, and communication, OSCE allows for objective assessment using standardized checklists (Gupta et al., 2010). It also evaluates critical professional abilities such as problem-solving, teaching, and managing unpredictable patient behavior, which are difficult to measure through traditional examinations (Jain et al., 1998; Jason et al., 1997).

Definition of OSCE

Harden (1988) described OSCE as a structured approach to assessing clinical competence, where components are systematically evaluated with emphasis on objectivity. Watson et al. (2002) similarly defined it as an assessment in which students demonstrate competence under simulated conditions. OSCE is organized so that all candidates are examined on identical content, by the same examiners, and according to predetermined guidelines. Feedback is systematically collected from both students and examiners (Gupta et al., 2010). Zayyan (2011) emphasized its versatility, noting that OSCE uses multiple stations where candidates perform clinical tasks within set timeframes, assessed against explicit criteria.

Review of Related Works

Some studies were conducted Objective Structured Clinical Examination and its Application in Nursing and Midwifery Professional Examinations in different parts of the world. Goh et al (2019) conducted a study on Objective structured clinical examinations (OSCEs) have been used globally in medical education and touted as the "gold standard" for competence-based assessments. However, the value of OSCEs in nursing education has not been extensively evaluated. The review aims to report the global trends in nursing OSCEs; evaluate their validity, reliability, acceptability, and costs; and present the characteristics of validated nursing OSCEs. The study was a scoping review involving a systematic search in 7 electronic databases. The results of the review showed that a total of 204 studies, published between 1982 and 2018, were included in the review. The review found that nursing OSCEs were extensively used across various nursing specialties in 33 countries and confirmed their validity, reliability, and acceptability in nursing education.

Cheng et al (2021) conducted a study on the objective structured clinical examination as an assessment strategy for clinical competence in novice nursing practitioners in Taiwan, Using a Quasi-experimental study (pre-post). Fifty-five novice nursing practitioners received the OSCE three-months following their graduation, which consisted of four stations: history taking, physical examination, problem-directed management, interpersonal communication, and the required techniques of related procedures. The results showed that among the novice nursing practitioners, 41 of them (74.5 %) passed the exam with a mean score of 61.38 ± 8.34 . There was a significantly higher passing rate among nurses who were working in medical-surgical wards (85.7 %) and the intensive care unit-emergency department (77.8 %) compared to novice nursing practitioners working in other units.

Ha and Lim (2023) evaluated the effects of the OSCE on the core nursing skills of 207 pre-licensure nursing students in Korea. We measured the nursing students' confidence, skills, and knowledge acquisition and retention. A one-way analysis of variance and Fisher's least significant difference were used for data analysis. Among the four nursing areas (fall, transfusion, pre-operative, and post-operative), students demonstrated the highest confidence level scores in pre-operative nursing. On the OSCE, students scored the highest in transfusion nursing. Significant differences were found between prior knowledge, knowledge acquisition, and retention. Our findings confirm that the OSCE, after lectures and core nursing skill practice, improved the retention of nursing students' knowledge. Therefore, this program can positively influence nursing students' knowledge level, and implementing the OSCE can strengthen students' clinical competency.

Miguel et al (2025) conducted a study on Application of the objective structured clinical examination in undergraduate nursing students: A systematic review with meta-synthesis. In conducting the review the studies were selected based on inclusion criteria such as nursing student focus, mention of OSCE, and discussion of competencies and perceptions. Searches were conducted from December 2024 to March 2025. Risk of bias was assessed, and data were synthesized using Microsoft Excel. The results of the review showed that twenty-five studies including 3,605 students were included. OSCE designs varied widely. Students described OSCE as objective and beneficial, though anxiety-inducing due to realism and time pressure.

Applications in Nursing and Midwifery Professional Examinations

The use of OSCE in nursing education has expanded significantly in the past decade (Milutinovic, 2013). OSCEs may serve both formative and summative purposes. Formative OSCEs provide immediate feedback, enhance learning, and prepare students for clinical placements (Carraccio et al., 2000; Nulty et al., 2011). Summative OSCEs, on the other hand, are used at the end of courses or modules to evaluate competence against set objectives (Taras, 2005).

In Nigeria, the NMCN, as the regulatory body, administers OSCE primarily as a summative assessment. The Council first introduced OSCE in midwifery examinations, and following its success, extended it to general nursing in 2018 to align with global best practices. Nursing and midwifery training institutions have also incorporated OSCE into their internal clinical assessments (NMC, 2010).

OSCE Setup

The number of OSCE stations typically ranges from 12 to 30, with 20 stations often considered sufficient. Each station usually lasts 5 minutes, though the ACGME recommends 10–15 minutes to allow for broader assessment. All candidates begin simultaneously, and the number of students should not exceed the number of stations. If necessary, parallel sessions or multiple sittings may be arranged. The entire examination is usually completed within 60–150 minutes (Gupta et al., 2010).

Blueprinting and Station Preparation

Blueprinting is a critical step in OSCE design. It involves mapping test content to course objectives and expected competencies. A two-dimensional grid is often used: one axis lists competencies (e.g., history taking, counseling, procedures), while the other lists clinical systems or problems (e.g., cardiovascular assessment, nutritional evaluation). This ensures balanced coverage of skills and enhances validity (Gupta et al., 2010).

Clinical competencies, including psychomotor and affective skills, should be prioritized. OSCEs can test a wide range of abilities, from data gathering to problem-solving and communication.

Types of OSCE Stations

OSCE stations are generally categorized as **procedure stations** or **question stations**. Procedure stations involve direct observation of clinical tasks, while question stations require written or verbal responses. Harden's original OSCE design paired each procedure station with a related question station, allowing assessment of both process and knowledge while minimizing cueing. Rest stations are also recommended every 30–40 minutes to provide breaks and allow logistical adjustments (Gupta et al., 2010).

Figure 2: OSCE consists of a circuit of stations which are usually connected in series (Adopted from Gupta, et al., 2010)

CONCLUSION

Given its structured and objective nature, OSCE has become an indispensable tool for assessing clinical competence in nursing and midwifery education. Its effective application in professional examinations contributes to the production of competent, versatile nurses and midwives who are well-equipped to deliver safe, high-quality care.

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